

A Modification of Pervier and Gortner's Method for the Estimation of Pentosans in Plant Tissues.

BY R. C. MALHOTRA.

The physiological importance of pentosans in enabling a plant to survive severe temperature conditions has recently been recognised. The writer's work showed a need for testing out some of the accepted methods, at present used in American laboratories.

Pentosans are generally estimated by one of the two methods, namely, biological and chemical, whose detailed procedure is being recorded hereinafter. The former is based on the assumption that pentosans are not fermented by yeasts, and the latter on the conversion of pentosans into furfural by hydrochloric or sulphuric acid.

Spoehr (*Carnegie Inst. Pub.*, 1919, No. 287, p. 36) emphasises that fermentation is the most reliable method in the quantitative estimation of pentosans.

Salkowski (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1900, **30**, 478; 1902, **34**, 162), Cremer (*Z. Biol.*, 1892, **29**, 484), Neuberg and Wohlegemuth (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1902, **35**, 31), Frankland and MacGregor (*Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 800), Behrens (*Centr. Bact.*, 1898, **2**, 547), Peterson, Fred and Schmidt (*J. Biochem.*, 1922, **54**, 19; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, **60**, 627), Tollen and others (*Annalen*, 1888, **249**, 257), Hawkins (*Amer. J. Bot.*, 1915, **2**, 375) and many other workers have shown the utilization of various organisms under varied conditions in such an estimation. Recently Rosa (*Missouri Ag. Exp. Sta. Res. Bull.*, 1921, No. 48) used Fleischmann's yeast for this purpose.

On the other hand, many chemists, such as Haas and Hill ("Chemistry of Plant Products"), Plimmer ("Practical Bio and Organic Chemistry"), Bokorny (*Chem. Abs.*, 1917, **11**, 2813), Englis and Hale (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 446), Conrad (*Missouri Ag. Exp. Sta. Res. Bull.*, 1926, No. 85), Bartholomew and Robbins (*Amer. J. Bot.*, 1926, **13**, 342), Davis and Sawyer (*J. Ag.*

Sci., 1914, 6, 406), and Abbott (*Missouri Ag. Exp. Sta. Res. Bull.*, 1926, No. 85) question the advisability of the fermentation methods.

The chemical methods depend upon the conversion of pentoses into furfural by the action of sulphuric or hydrochloric acid. The sulphuric acid method with the modification that hydrazone be precipitated in the presence of sodium chloride (a tedious process) was recommended by the United States Department of Agriculture. However, Ling and Nanji (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 466) tried to overcome this inconvenience by displacing the gasometric method by the iodometric one. The writer's experience shows that even this method is not very reliable. These authors used an extract of a few Indian grasses only. The writer has obtained some data (to be published shortly), which indicate that a fair percentage of pentosans cannot be extracted. Link (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2506) has also shown that xylan is mixed up with cellulose of the cell wall.

Pervier and Gortner (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 1167) found that in the official method ("Assoc. Official Agri. Chemists," 1920, p. 96) the reaction took place in 18 to 20 per cent. instead of 12 per cent. hydrochloric acid as is assumed, and that the acid of this concentration has destructive influence on furfural. They recommended the use of a slow current of steam through the distilling mixture to carry away the furfural as rapidly as it is formed. Its destruction by long contact with strong acid, however, has not been much avoided as they had expected. The delivery tube as used by them does not carry steam to all points alike, consequently, all parts of the mixture have not the same rate of reaction. Further they did not regulate the flow of steam.

Regarding the estimation of furfural in the distillate, one of the promising methods seems to be that of Powell and Whittaker (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 35T). Recently Deshpande (*J. Indian Inst. Sci., Bangalore*, Vol. 13A, Part 9) found Powell and Whittaker's method to be the most accurate.

Numerous other methods have been suggested, such as Jolles's (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1906, 45, 196) method of titration with sodium bisulphite, titration with phenylhydrazine and with Fehling's solution and thiobarbituric acid method; but all these are open to serious errors (*Carnegie Inst. Wash. Pub.*, 1919, No. 287). Pervier and Gortner tried several new methods unsuccessfully.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Materials.—McIntosh and Winter banana apples and tomatoes were used. The apple twigs were collected from a very uniform plot at the New York Agricultural Experiment Station, Geneva, N. Y. The tomato seeds were obtained from Professor Yeager of North Dakota, Fargo, out of his pure bred stock. The plants were grown at a uniform temperature of 50° at the University of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois. Three-year old apple twigs and tomato without roots were used. They were cut into small pieces, dried at 100° for one hour to kill all the enzymes present as recommended by Murneek (*Proc. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.*, 1928, 125, 338), dried for 26 hours at 75°, cooled in a desiccator, ground, pulverized in a Wiley mill until they passed through a sieve with 80 meshes per inch, and collected. From these samples about 3 g. of material (in triplicate) were used for each of the experiments, except in Rosa and Spoehr's methods, where 10 g. samples were used. Pure xylan, which was purified by Wheeler and Tollen's method (*Annalen*, 1889, 254, 304), was tried first.

Methods: A.—For the official method the sample was heated with 100 c.c. of 12% hydrochloric acid at such a rate that 30 c.c. of the distillate passed over in 10 minutes. Thirty c.c. more of the acid were added and the process was repeated till 360 c.c. of the distillate were obtained. This was made up to 400 c.c. by adding 12% hydrochloric acid and the furfural estimated as phloroglucide in the usual manner.

B.—In Pervier and Gortner's method a slow current of steam was used, other conditions being the same as in A.

C.—In Ling and Nanji's method, the outlines of these authors were followed, except that instead of 10 c.c. of *N*/10-iodine solutions, 20 c.c. were used. The excess of iodine was titrated against *N*/20-sodium thiosulphate.

D.—In Spoehr's method, the samples were heated with 1% hydrochloric acid under reflux for 3 hours, 40 c.c. of the acid being used for every 2 grams. The hydrolysed extract was divided into aliquots and adjusted to the desired hydrogen ion concentration with *N*/10-sodium hydroxide. Gillespie's (*Soil Sci.*, 1920, 9, 115) colorimetric method was used in determining the hydrogen ion concentration before and after sterilization and after fermentation. The reaction of the media was maintained at p_{H} 7.0 (neutral point).

To the sterilized neutral sample obtained, was added baker's yeast mixture, made to a thin paste by using 0.2 g. pressed yeast per g. of the original sample. Every time a fresh preparation of carefully washed baker's yeast was used, since it was realised that foreign substances in the yeast might cause an error. The vessel was stoppered with sterilized cotton and incubated for 40 hours at 35° as directed by Abbott (*loc. cit.*).

E.—In Rosa's method, Fleischmann's yeast cake was used. The solutions were not sterilized, but 8 per cent. alcohol was added before fermentation to prevent the growth of surface films, unless the fermentation was continued longer than 5 days.

In (D) and (E) the analyses were calculated in terms of c.c. of standardized Fehling's solution, reduced to one gram of fresh dry sample. The normality of copper sulphate solution used for making Fehling's solution was found by electrolytic method. The reducing value of the solutions was determined by heating with Fehling's solution, centrifuging and determining the copper sulphate left in an aliquot of the supernatant liquid by the method of Peters (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **34**, 928). Proper dextrose-copper factor as carefully determined by Peters and plotted by Abbott was used.

A suggested modified method.—An apparatus (Fig. 1) was set up.

Fig. 1.

In flask A 100 c.c. of 3 per cent. hydrochloric acid was put through a separating funnel *a*. Flask A was connected with flask B by a perforated tube, which was placed in such a manner that a current of steam coming from the flask A would react equally with the contents of the flask B, which contained the sample, plus 100 c.c. of 9 per cent. hydrochloric acid. The stoppers were made

air tight with shellac. The distillate from condenser *C* was received in flasks *D* and *E*. The use of two catching flasks was necessary as a safety device against the back flow of the distillate. Flask *E* was connected with a suction bottle *F*, with which a safety device *g*, a tubing connecting suction pump *h* and a manometer *I* were attached. Both *h* and *g* could be used for reducing the suction pressure at will. Every precaution was taken to have all the connections air tight.

When the contents of flask *B* became hot, steam was released from flask *A* at such a rate that 100 c.c. of the distillate collected in flasks *D* and *E* per hour, more solutions were poured through the separating funnel maintaining the original volume. This was repeated until the distillate collected was 380 c.c. The discharge of the steam current was very slow. It could be regulated by means of a uniform but desired heat of the flame.

The steam current and the suction pressure formed a system having the least danger of the destruction of furfural. At no time hydrochloric acid was higher than 11%. The total pressure used was 15 cm. The subsequent operations were identical with those of the official method. This method gave very uniform results. The figures for pentosans were higher than any other existing chemical methods. As to the biological methods, as advocated by Spoehr and by Rosa, the results were so fluctuating, at least in the writer's experiments, that the data seemed to show a great unreliability of the use of these methods in the determination of pentosans. The results are being presented in Table I.

TABLE I.
Pentosan Content of Plant Tissues in Terms of Fresh Weight as Determined by Various Methods.

Tissue and lot.	Chemical methods.			Biological methods.		
	Official.	Pervier and Gortner's.	Ling and Nanji's.	Spoebr's.	Rosa's.	Pervier and Gortner's modified method.
I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
McIntosh apple						
A	5.810%	5.753%	6.031%	7.321%	6.173%	6.245%
B	5.372	5.981	6.328	2.834	3.533	6.292
C	5.526	6.012	5.812	4.951	2.827	6.331
Winter banana apple						
A	5.332	5.371	5.171	4.819	5.481	5.893
B	5.181	5.231	5.231	5.332	4.139	5.788
C	5.311	5.522	5.711	4.213	3.620	5.914
Tomato						
A	0.211	0.180	0.200	0.200	0.015	0.301
B	0.190	0.198	0.193	0.051	0.111	0.317
C	0.161	0.201	0.101	0.118	0.187	0.321
Pure pentosans (xylan)						
A	95.8	96.3	96.0	70.9	79.3	96.8
B	95.3	96.4	96.1	78.3	83.2	96.9
C	95.0	96.0	96.5	91.9	91.1	96.8

N.B.—Biological methods were again carried out in fives. Their general tendency seemed to be the same as indicated in Columns V and VI.

Discussion.

It will be seen from Column II, that the official method has given low and comparatively less uniform figures, which for pure pentosans are somewhat low also. Pervier and Gortner's method in the main (Column III) gave somewhat higher values than the official method, although they were not the highest. Furthermore, the percentages were not uniform. In case of pure pentosans figures agreed fairly well among themselves and reached near the maximum probable yield.

The main source of some error in Pervier and Gortner's method has already been pointed out. Absence of uniformity in this as well as in the official method may be attributed to the following factors: (a) some material adheres against the walls of the vessels. The tubing delivering steam cannot possibly react with this adherent material due to lack of perforation. (b) The incoming and the outgoing steam are not properly regulated. (c) There is still a higher concentration of hydrochloric acid with which the contents of the flask come in contact.

Figures by Ling and Nanji's method (Column IV) are not very constant. In some cases they are lower than those obtained by Pervier and Gortner's method, although, on the whole, they are higher than those in Columns II and III, except for the pure pentosans. The author thinks that this method (no matter how convenient it may appear) has the least satisfaction of all the chemical methods suggested, up to now, for the estimation of pentosans.

Of the biological methods (Columns V and VI) it seems that both Spoehr and Rosa's methods are unreliable, because they yield lower figures. In comparing these methods with any of the chemical methods, it may be noted that, in the main, chemical methods are more satisfactory, at least with these tissues. The writer agrees with those who have already noted the unreliability of fermentation methods. It seems to the writer that until we learn more about the specific nutrition of various organisms and the conditions under which combined carbon can be used by them, biological methods will remain unsafe in this type of problems.

According to the writer's method (Column VII) it seems, that on the whole, pentosan content is higher than any method. For instance by the modified method, average figures of McIntosh apple indicate a difference of approximately 12.4% for the official, 8.0% for Pervier

and Gortner's, 5% for Ling and Nanji's, 21% for Spoehr's and 65% for Rosa's methods. All other averages are also high, although the figures for pure pentosans do not seem to show such a divergence. The analysis of pure pentosans by means of the different chemical methods with the exception of the official method, shows hardly any difference. It seems that the destruction of pentosans by these methods is in a small measure due to these reagents (except in the official method), but mainly due to the effect of foreign matters on pentosans. When there are substances other than pentosans, as found in a plant tissue, the reagents may induce the formation of stable non-volatile products with furfural, or the decomposition of furfural. It may be probable also, that the pentosans present in plant change into furfural and some other products, while pure pentosans give only furfural. More work has to be done before such conclusions can be warranted. No claim has been made to study the effect of methyl or hydroxymethylfurfural, pectic or uronic acids on the result.

Conclusions.

A modification of Pervier and Gortner's method for the pentosan determination has been proposed, which seems to yield higher and uniform results. Biological methods seem to have many sources of error and are therefore unreliable. No claim has been made that this method has any advantage over other chemical methods (except the official) for the pure pentosans.

It is a pleasure to thank Dr. Karl P. Link, Associate Professor of Agricultural Chemistry, University of Wisconsin, Madison, for a supply of xylan and to Miss Elvera Hanket of Northwestern University for going through the MS.

GRADUATE SCHOOL OF SCIENCE,
UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO,
CHICAGO, ILLINOIS, U.S.A.

Received June 2, 1939.